

A Text Mining Pipeline Using Active and Deep Learning Aimed at Curating Information in Computational Neuroscience

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Abstract

The curation of neuroscience entities is crucial to ongoing efforts in neuroinformatics and computational neuroscience, such as those being deployed in the context of continuing large-scale brain modelling projects. However, manually sifting through thousands of articles for new information about modelled entities is a painstaking and low-reward task. Text mining can be used to help a curator extract relevant information from this literature in a systematic way. We propose the application of text mining methods for the neuroscience literature. Specifically, we engaged two computational neuroscientists to annotate a corpus of entities pertinent to neuroscience using active learning techniques to enable swift, targeted annotation. We then trained machine learning models to recognise the entities that have been identified. We tested a traditional rule-based approach, a conditional random field and a model using deep learning named entity recognition, finding that the deep learning model was superior. Our final results show that we can detect a range of named entities of interest to the neuroscientist with a macro average precision, recall and F1 score of 0.866, 0.817 and 0.837 respectively.

Background

International projects such as the European Human Brain Project and the United States' BRAIN initiative have recently emerged in neuroscience and are pushing traditional neuroscience toward the big science paradigm (Underwood 2016). At their heart, these projects harness big data to model in great detail the functioning of the brain at the level of the neuron. The data-driven approach adopted for such large-scale modelling requires the definition of numerous entities (e.g., neuron, synapses, ion channels). Although the characterization of the structural and functional aspects of these entities can partly be assessed in the laboratory, the complexity and the cross-scale nature of the modelled phenomena prohibit a comprehensive evaluation of all aspects at play. Thus, experimental data must be complemented with the scientific knowledge accumulated world-wide and recorded in the scholarly literature, a state of affairs responsible for increasing the recognition of the need for large and high-quality databases of literature-curated information. Although recently reaching more awareness, this need has long been recognized and previously motivated large and enduring curation projects in the life sciences, such as UniProt for proteins (The UniProt Consortium 2017). For neuroscience, many efforts have been deployed to categorise and define the types of entities described across the neuroscience literature (e.g., KnowledgeSpace, NeuroLex) and some high-quality databases are now available, such as NeuroElectro (Tripathy et al. 2014) which records a large number of values for a representative, although limited, number of neuronal modelling parameters.

To promote traceability and reusability of systematically curated literature for the large number of parameters needed for detailed data-driven modelling of the brain, a new manual curation framework has been recently proposed (O'Reilly et al. 2017). However, this manual process requires a team of

curators to sift through abstracts and full texts to be able to identify new entities and their properties. This is a slow and painstaking process, which requires a curator to maintain a mixture of specialist domain knowledge alongside the necessary informatics knowledge to ensure that they are able to discover all the relevant documents for a new entity. Furthermore, a curator's work is never finished. The meaning of terms may shift over time and new terms may be created as the collective understanding of the field changes and new material is published. What then can we do to help the beleaguered curator? Text Mining can come to their aid. We can use a variety of techniques to lift the burden of informatics from the curator and allow them to focus on applying their own specialist domain knowledge to the entities in question. In this paper, we propose such a system for the curation of a number of neuroscience entities. By identifying these entities automatically in text, we can help the curator to quickly survey the literature for papers of interest. Whereas the research of others has reported text mining techniques for neuroscience previously, such as WhiteText (French et al. 2012) or Textpresso (Müller et al. 2008), our methods apply state of the art text mining techniques to the neuroscience literature, targeting a wide set of entity types with state of the art performance (as measured by the standard metrics of precision, recall and F1).

Early work on text mining for neuroscience focussed on the area of document classification (Craστο et al. 2003; Van Driel et al. 2006). In this task, properties of documents and entities are assembled and then processed to provide some meaningful information, such as identifying relations between phenotypes (Van Driel et al. 2006), or to populate neuroscience databases (Craστο et al. 2003). This work continues more recently, targeted towards literature surveys (Balan et al. 2014) and information retrieval (Lapish et al. 2013). Document classification is useful when a user needs to find relevant documents or entities from a large collection, however it can only tell a user in which document the relevant information is contained.

To further target the valuable information held in documents, researchers can draw on the technique of named entity recognition. In this technique, a researcher first typically establishes the categories of named entities that they are interested in. They then manually annotate a corpus of documents with examples of the entity types. A named entity recogniser can then be trained using these examples via one of a number of standard libraries, such as CRF++¹, or NERSuite². The named entity recogniser can then be applied to further documents, or document collections. The results of named entity recognition can then be used in further tasks such as curation (Ambert et al. 2013), information retrieval (Müller et al. 2008) and inference (Pan et al. 2006). Notable efforts to create named entity recognition tools for neuroscience have focussed on the identification of brain regions (French et al. 2009; French et al. 2012), neurons (Ambert et al. 2013), brain connectivity (Vasques et al. 2015; Richardet et al. 2015), and a number of entities related to spinal cord injuries (Stöckel et al. 2015).

In addition to identifying named entities in a text, researchers may also wish to identify relations between the entities that they extract. Identifying relations between entities adds an extra dimension of information and can help to understand how the entities are being used. It may be helpful for filtering out unwanted entities in future processing. In neuroscience, French et al. (2012) used relation extraction techniques to identify connectivity statements between brain regions. This work was continued by Richardet et al. (2013), with some improvements.

The Textpresso text mining framework for neuroscience (Müller et al. 2008) is designed to help people search through neuroscience research papers by providing a semantic search interface. Users can enter names of entities from one of a number of predefined categories and are shown documents which contain their entity of choice. The system also handles relations, allowing a user to filter documents based on entities occurring in a number of relation types. Evaluation by Balan et al. (2014) showed that Textpresso was useful in the context of performing a literature survey. The Textpresso system relies on a large dictionary of terms, which are matched against the text of documents to identify named entities. This technique is less powerful than the CRF/deep learning approaches that we have investigated, as it is constrained to identifying entities that occur in the dictionary and cannot identify new occurrences, or variants of terms.

Named entity recognition requires annotated data, which can be time consuming to produce, however techniques exist to reduce the number of documents that need to be annotated, whilst retaining strong

¹ <https://taku910.github.io/crfpp/>

² <http://nersuite.nlplab.org/>

performance. Active learning is a method of selecting sentences which will provide the most informative examples for a named entity recognition tool to learn from. Active learning has been applied widely for named entity recognition tasks (Kim et al. 2006; Settles and Craven 2008; Y. Chen et al. 2015; D. Shen et al. 2004), as well as being applied for the recognition of neurons (Ambert et al. 2013). The alternative to using active learning would be to manually annotate entire documents, however using active learning allows us to attain high performance with minimal manual annotation effort.

To automatically recognise named entities in text, the standard approach has been to use the conditional random field (CRF) (Lafferty et al. 2001). Typical features have included, for each token: the part-of-speech, lemma and other surface features. Standard libraries such as NERSuite and CRF++ are freely available, lowering the barrier to entry for this approach. A new trend in named entity recognition is to use recent developments in the field of deep learning to create contextual embedding representations of a sentence that can be used as input to a CRF. This has been shown to be a very powerful approach, and led to an improved state of the art performance on a number of natural language processing tasks (Huang et al. 2015; Rao et al. 2016; D. Chen and Manning 2014), especially when combined with active learning (Y. Shen et al. 2017). Our approach, based upon the work of Lample et al. (2016), is described in further detail in the next section.

Methods

Entity Definitions

For this work, we annotated only entities that are specific members of a generic class (e.g., ‘pyramidal neurons’ are a specific member of the generic class ‘neurons’). Mentions of the generic class (e.g., “These *neurons* are known to be [...]”) have not been annotated, only specific entities (e.g., “The input resistance of *thalamo-cortical cells* [...]”). Adjective forms (e.g., cortical) of corresponding entities (e.g., cortex) have not been separately annotated. In many instances, boundaries defining an entity were found to be intrinsically fuzzy. Thus, to provide reproducible manual annotations, we found it necessary to define clear rules about what is annotated or not. Although, some of these rules may appear subjective or arbitrary, they were necessary to clarify borderline cases.

We annotated six types of entities.

Neurons

Mention of types of neurons (e.g., *Martinotti cells*), the electrically excitable cells of the nervous system. We included in the annotation all the qualifiers that define the cell types, for example the brain region (e.g., *the thalamo-cortical relay cell of the ventrobasal complex*).

Brain Regions

This entity is defined as being any sequence of tokens referring to a specific area of the brain. This includes for example cortical layers (e.g., *layer 1 of the cortex*), areas mentioned by their function (e.g., *the somatosensory area of the thalamus*), but excludes the mention of a system (e.g., the somatosensory system) or of a “representation” (e.g., the shoulder representation).

Experimental Values

This is a broad class of quantifiable values (including the unit, if present) that can be reported in a paper, defining either the experimental context or the results of an experiment. It could be defining a range (e.g., *-100 to -40 mV*) or be a list of values all related to the same entities (e.g., repeated measurements). However, two values separated by a conjunction (e.g., “with *0.13* and *0.20 ms* respectively”) have been annotated separately if referring to different entities (e.g., two different cell types). Sample sizes were not annotated as an experimental value.

Units

Units which describe a scientific quantity, possibly as defined by the International System of Units. These often occur as abbreviations. A unit can in some cases be a noun or phrase that is not typically thought of as a unit (e.g., *20 spikes per stimulation period*).

Ion Currents, Channels, and Conductances

These three entities have been distinguished and annotated separately to help better define their scope. They are closely related (i.e., an ion current is generated by the flow of ions through ion channels, and the behaviour of the channel can be modelled by its conductance), thus often the annotations of these three entities are very similar, just differing by their last part (e.g., *T-type Ca²⁺ channels*, *T-type Ca²⁺ currents*, *T-type Ca²⁺ conductance*). These entities can often be referred to by the name of their protein (e.g., Cav3.1 ion channels) or of their coding gene (e.g., CACNA1G). References to only a sub-domain of an ion channel have not been annotated, unless they were used to refer to a channel variety (e.g., alpha1G, a type of alpha subunit, is often used as synonym for Cav3.1 ion channels). In general, alpha sub-units can give their name to the channel type, not beta sub-units, at least for sodium and calcium. In case of genetically modified animals referred to as *gene_name*-/- where the *gene_name* is associated with a knock-down ion channel, we annotated the *gene_name* as (a reference to) an ion channel (e.g., “Both tonic and burst spikes were observed in *CaV3.1*^{+/+} TC cells, whereas only tonic spikes were detected in *CaV3.1*^{-/-} TC cells”).

Model organism

We use the entity model organism as a broad concept, not distinguishing species, strains, or genetic mutation. Similarly, we also use this entity to annotate classes of species (e.g., rodent). Species may be referred to via an informal name (e.g., rabbit) as well as the formal Latin name (e.g., *Oryctolagus Cuniculus*). Strings with implicit mention of a model organism have also been annotated. This is the case for example when talking about a strain and its wild-type counterpart; wild-type is not in itself a species but is referring to species entity (i.e., the wild-type counterpart of an experimental strain previously mentioned). For the same reason, “normal rat” was annotated (including the “normal” qualifier) when used to contrast to another strain (e.g., Genetic Absence Epilepsy Rat from Strasbourg) and is implicitly used as a synonym for “wild type”.

Corpus Annotation

We initially ran a pilot annotation with one annotator (COR), a computational neuroscientist, of 15 abstracts from neuroscience articles. We used this pilot study to understand the requirements of the annotations for the targeted use case and to give the curator some training material so that they could familiarize themselves with the annotation tool. This preliminary phase was also essential to create clear annotation guidelines that define the scope of the entities, thereby promoting high inter-annotator agreement. We used the brat rapid annotation tool (Stenetorp et al. 2012) for all our annotations. For our next round of annotation, we used active learning. We collected 160 abstracts relevant to neuroscience and processed these using the active learning selection criteria described below. We were able to use the 15 abstracts we had annotated earlier as the seed documents for our active learning method. The top 500 sentences were selected after active learning and were annotated by our annotator. In our final round of annotation, we collected 15 full text papers related to neuroscience. We used the 500 sentences that had been annotated in the first round as our seed set for the second round of active learning.

To ensure consistency in our annotations we asked a second annotator (EI, also a computational neuroscientist) to doubly annotate the first 200 sentences from each of the two active learning rounds. This allowed us to calculate inter-annotator agreement using F1-score. Through discussions of discrepancies between the two sets of annotations, we noted a number of areas for clarification, which were incorporated into the guidelines. All other annotations were updated as the guidelines were updated. Aside from consulting on borderline or ambiguous cases, both curators performed their work blindly with respect to (1) each other’s annotations, (2) the results of inter-annotator agreement and (3) the results of named entity recognition tools that were created using the corpus that was being produced.

An active learning criterion can help to identify which sequences are informative in an unlabelled dataset. These informative sequences are useful for training a high performance named entity recognition model. In our annotation process, we used an uncertainty based active learning criterion: ‘normalized entropy’ (Kim et al. 2006). The uncertainty based methods have been shown to lead to an early increase in performance when annotating selected sequences from a dataset (Settles and Craven 2008). This criterion assumes that the most informative unlabelled sequences are those for which the current named entity recognizer is most uncertain about the predicted sequence of labels. Given an unlabelled sequence \mathbf{x} and a set Y of labels, \mathbf{y} is defined as a label sequence for \mathbf{x} and $y_i \in Y$ is the corresponding named entity label of x_i . x_i is the i -th word in sequence \mathbf{x} . $P(\mathbf{y}|\mathbf{x})$ is the conditional

probability of \mathbf{y} under the sequence \mathbf{x} . The steps that measure the informativeness of \mathbf{x} are as follows. In the first place, we use the current model to predict the label sequence for \mathbf{x} and select the top- N best predicted label sequences $\{\mathbf{y}^{(1)}, \mathbf{y}^{(2)}, \dots, \mathbf{y}^{(N)}\}$ with the highest probabilities $\{\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{y}^{(1)}|\mathbf{x}), \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{y}^{(2)}|\mathbf{x}), \dots, \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{y}^{(N)}|\mathbf{x})\}$. Secondly, the entropy of sequence \mathbf{x} is defined based on these conditional probabilities of the top- N label sequences:

$$\text{Entropy}(\mathbf{x}) = - \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{P(\mathbf{y}^{(i)}|\mathbf{x})}{\sum_{j=1}^N P(\mathbf{y}^{(j)}|\mathbf{x})} \log_2 \left[\frac{P(\mathbf{y}^{(i)}|\mathbf{x})}{\sum_{j=1}^N P(\mathbf{y}^{(j)}|\mathbf{x})} \right]$$

Thirdly, we use the formula below to normalize the entropy to $[0,1]$.

$$\text{Normalized_Entropy}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\text{Entropy}(\mathbf{x})}{-\log_2 \frac{1}{N}}$$

An unlabelled sequence with a high normalized entropy score is considered informative and its corresponding annotated label sequence is likely to be useful to improve the performance of the current model. In our experiments, we set $N = 3$ and use CRF++ to obtain the top- N predicted label sequences with conditional probabilities for each unlabelled sequence in a dataset.

Rules and Dictionaries

We implemented a number of dictionary and rule based methods of identifying the entities that we are interested in.

We used the online resource ‘NeuroLex’ and extracted the names and synonyms of all entities belonging to the following classes: Brain Region (id:birnlex_1167), Neuron (id:sao1417703748), Model Organism (id:nlx_89357), Ionic Channel (id:oen_0001181), Ionic Current (id:nifext_8054) and Ionic Conductance (id:oen_0001224). We adapted our list of ionic currents to represent names of ionic conductances augmenting our list of ionic conductances (using the replacement ‘current’ to ‘conductance’, where appropriate). We also converted acronyms for currents by replacing ‘I’ with ‘g’ (e.g. ‘IH’ to ‘gH’). We used the NERSuite Dictionary matcher to match entities to their dictionary entries.

We used regular expressions to identify Neurons, Ionic Channels, Ionic Conductances and Ionic Currents. These were developed based on the typical names of an ionic current. We employed a syntactic parser to identify the noun phrase containing a matched regular expression and assigned the whole noun phrase to be of the matched annotation type. The regular expressions were as follows:

- Neurons: `.*(neuron(e?s)?)(cells?)(.*)`
- Ionic Current: `.*(current)s?`
- Ionic Channel: `.*(channel)s?`
- Ionic Conductance: `.*(conductance)s?`

To detect Scientific units, we employed a gazetteer which provided information about each unit in question. The Gazetteer we employed contained 24 unit names (volt, gram, etc.), which could be combined with 19 standard prefixes (milli, kilo, etc.) to give complex unit names (milligram, kilometre, etc.). Short forms of units and prefixes were also included to give abbreviated unit names (mg, km, mm, etc.)

Scientific Values were detected by first identifying any potential values in a text using the regular expression:

`\d+(\,|\d{3})*(\.\d+)?`

Any numbers that were detected with this regular expression were linked to scientific units that had been discovered using the gazetteer approach. A number was linked to a value if it was within the same noun phrase as that value. This accounted for longer dependencies, such as ranges or lists of values where the unit is only present at the end. E.g., “10-20mv”, “15, 30 and 45 millimetres”.

In addition to the above we used Acromine (Okazaki and Ananiadou 2006; Okazaki et al. 2010) to link common acronyms to their expanded forms. Acromine draws upon the whole of MEDLINE to generate acronyms for common terms. If any of the expanded forms were annotated elsewhere in the text, we assigned the same annotation type to the acronym in question.

Conditional Random Field

We used the NERSuite implementation of the conditional random field for named entity recognition. NERSuite relies on several features for each token in the data. An example of the features that were created by NERSuite is shown in Table 1, where the sentence ‘*Abstract: Whole-cell coltage recordings were made in vivo in the ventral posterior medial nucleus (VPM)*’ has been annotated with features by NERSuite.

Table 1: The features that were generated for NERSuite at the token level.

Begin	End	Word	Lemma	POS	Chunk	Dictionary
0	8	Abstract	Abstract	NN	B-NP	O
9	10	:	:	:	O	O
11	16	Whole	Whole	JJ	B-NP	O
17	22	-cell	-cell	JJ	I-NP	O
23	30	voltage	voltage	NN	I-NP	O
31	41	recordings	recording	NNS	I-NP	O
42	46	were	be	VBD	B-VP	O
47	51	made	make	VBN	I-VP	O
52	54	in	in	FW	B-ADVP	O
55	59	vivo	vivo	FW	I-ADVP	O
60	62	in	in	IN	B-PP	O
63	66	the	the	DT	B-NP	O
67	74	ventral	ventral	JJ	I-NP	B-BrainRegion
75	84	posterior	posterior	JJ	I-NP	I-BrainRegion
85	91	medial	medial	JJ	I-NP	I-BrainRegion
92	99	nucleus	nucleus	NN	I-NP	I-BrainRegion
100	101	(((O	O
102	105	VPM	VPM	NN	B-NP	B-BrainRegion
106	107)))	O	O

The features in Table 1 are as follows:

- **Begin:** The starting offset of each word in terms of its character index.
- **End:** The index of the character immediately after the word. This ensures that subtracting the value for begin from the value for end will give the length of the token.
- **Word:** The raw wordform as it appeared in the text
- **Lemma:** The base form of the word – found by dictionary lookup. (e.g. ‘were’ becomes ‘be’, ‘made’ becomes ‘make’).
- **POS:** the part of speech of the word provided by the GENIA tagger (Tsuruoka et al. 2005). This indicates whether a noun, verb, adjective, adverb or something else was present. The codes used above are as follows: NN=Noun, NNS = Plural noun, VBD= Past tense of verb, VBN = Past participle of verb, DT = Determiner, JJ = adjective, IN = Preposition and FW = Foreign word.
- **Chunk:** the syntactic chunk that the text currently represents. B- I- and O represent Begin, Inside and Outside, respectively. NP= Noun Phrase, VP = Verb Phrase, ADVP = Adverb Phrase, PP = Prepositional Phrase.
- **Dictionary:** We added dictionary features for all entities apart from the Value entity (where it was not possible to create a valid dictionary). We used the dictionaries that we described in the section above. For units, we used the names of the units derived from the Gazetteer. B, I and O are as above. In the example, we have shown the dictionary entries for brain regions, hence B-BrainRegion indicates the beginning of a brain region mention and I-BrainRegion indicates that the token is still inside the Brain Region mention. When annotating other entity types, the appropriate dictionary is used.

Finally, the data was split into train, test and validation sets (although the validation set was only used for parameter tuning in the Deep Learning NER). For training and evaluation purposes, we added a further column of data to represent the gold standard annotation that our annotators had judged to be the correct set of labels for the entity type that was being classified. We trained a separate CRF model for each entity type and then tested each model on the held out test data.

Deep Learning NER

Long short-term memory (LSTM); (Hochreiter and Schmidhuber 1997) is a variant of the recurrent neural network (RNN), which uses a neural network to encode contextual information about a sequence. To capture features describing both past (left context) and future (right context) information associated with a given sequence, forward and backward LSTM (bi-directional LSTM) has been applied to many different classification tasks (Miwa and Bansal 2016; Habibi et al. 2017; Dligach et al. 2017) and performs very well compared with approaches relying on hand-crafted features. In our work, we use a model based on the work of Lample et al. (2016). We re-implemented their first model using Chainer³.

Figure 1: The neural network architecture that we used to produce the character embeddings.

Figure 2: The neural network architecture that we used to produce our output sequence of BIO labels

³ <https://chainer.org/>

Our model consists of four layers: embedding layer, character bidirectional LSTM layer, word bidirectional LSTM layer and CRF layer, as shown in Figure 2. Taking sequences and pre-trained word embeddings as the input, the model outputs sequences labelled with BIO (beginning, inside, outside of an entity) tags. Details are described next.

1) Embedding layer

Given a sequence $s = \{w_1, w_2, w_3, \dots, w_n\}$, w_i represents a word in this sequence. Firstly, a unique id is assigned to each word in the training data set to represent itself. Similarly, all the characters are mapped to a dictionary and each character in this dictionary is described by a unique integer. Therefore, each word can be represented by a word ID and a series of character IDs. Subsequently, two linear functions are separately applied to each word and its characters to generate two outputs: word vectors and a character-based word matrix. The row dimension of the character-based word matrix equals the length in characters of its word. Contrary to randomly initialised character-based word matrix, pre-trained word embeddings (Chiu et al. 2016) which were trained from a 2.7 billion word corpus from PubMed is applied to initialize each word vector. More specifically, words included in the pre-trained embeddings are assigned with corresponding vectors in the word embeddings while unknown words (those that do not appear in the embedding) are randomly initialized using a linear function. The pre-trained embeddings are trained with the skip-gram model on a large number of unannotated abstracts from PubMed.

2) Character bidirectional LSTM

Previous work has demonstrated orthographical features contribute to named entity recognition (Limsopatham et. al 2016; Bhasuran et. al 2016). Given a word, instead of using hand-crafted affix features, we use the BiLSTM to acquire character representations for each word. Suppose the character matrix of a given word is $C_{n \times m}$ where n and m mean the length of this word and the dimension character vector, respectively. We firstly feed this matrix to the forward LSTM and use the hidden state of the last character to represent left context information of the word. In the same way, the backward LSTM is employed to each column of the matrix in reverse order to generate right context information of this word. Next, we concatenate these two vectors as the character representation of this word. This is depicted in Figure 1.

3) Word bidirectional LSTM

For each word in the given sequence, the character representation acquired from the previous layer concatenated with the word representation constitute the input to this layer. To avoid over-fitting, we apply a common regularisation technique called “drop out” for each word before sending to BiLSTM. Then, forward and backward context representation acquired from the BiLSTM layer is connected, acting as the input to the CRF layer.

4) CRF layer

Context representation is fed into the CRF layer which considers neighbour information to decode the best label sequence.

The hyper parameters used in our model are shown in Table 2:

Table 2: The hyper paramters that were used during training of our model.

Hyper Parameter	Value
Epochs	20
Batch Size	10
Character embedding dimension	25
Word embedding dimension	200
Dropout rate	0.5
Character-based word embedding	250
Optimization method	Adam
Learning Rate	0.013
Weight decay	0.0001
Pre-trained word embeddings	PubMed-shuffle-win-2.bin (Chiu et al. 2016)

Results

In this section we present the results of the corpus creation process and the evaluation we performed on the corpus using the named entity recognition tools that we developed.

Corpus Creation

Inter annotator agreement was assessed using the F1 metric. This metric allows us to see how likely the two annotators were to agree on a given annotation class. It is more sensitive to disagreements than using percentage of agreement, as the F1 score is calculated as the harmonic mean of precision and recall and therefore will be low if either of these metrics is low. In addition, F1 Score only takes into account instances where annotators have agreed on a named entity, or where they have disagreed. It does not reward annotators for agreeing on words in a text which are not marked as named entities. This is important as named entities are sparse in a text and rewarding agreement on the absence of a named entity would overly bias the results. We present the results of the corpus creation process in Table 3.

Table 3: Final statistics on our corpus. We show a high level of agreement across all categories. Agreement is reported as F1 score.

Entity	Agreement	Number Double Annotated	Total
Brain Region	0.891	480	1,055
Neuron	0.825	309	767
Model Organism	0.846	150	299
Ionic Channel	0.639	83	201
Ionic Current	0.904	137	339
Ionic Conductance	0.810	50	76
Value	0.784	211	594
Unit	0.902	151	507
All	0.837	1,571	3,838

In Table 3, we have also included the number of double annotated entities, as well as the total number of annotated entities. One annotator annotated 500 sentences from abstracts and 500 further sentences from full papers. The other annotator annotated 200 sentences from the abstracts and 200 sentences from the full papers to allow us to calculate agreement.

Some examples of annotations from the full corpus are included below:

- (1) “Gramicidin -perforated patch-clamp recordings were made from slices of the *suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCN)* of adult rats”
(Brain Region: “*suprachiasmatic nucleus*”, “*SCN*”. Model Organism: “rats”)
- (2) The emergence of depolarizing GABA(A)-mediated responses in a subset of *SCN neurons* at night can be ascribed to a depolarizing shift in GABA(A) reversal potential.
(Neuron: “*SCN neurons*”)
- (3) Whole-cell *I(Ts)* amplitude was increased when Ba²⁺ was substituted for Ca²⁺ as the charge carrier.
(Ionic Current: “*I(Ts)*”)
- (4) FRB in this model is favored by enhancing *persistent g(Na)* and also by measures that reduce [Ca²⁺]_i or that reduce the *conductance of g(K(C))*
(Ionic Conductance: “*persistent g(Na)*”, “*conductance of g(K(C))*”)
- (5) Using in situ hybridization, we have localized central and peripheral nervous system expression of three transcripts (*alpha1G*, *alpha1H*, and *alpha1I*) of the *T-type calcium channel* family (*CaVT*).
(Ionic Channel: “*alpha1G*”, “*alpha1H*”, “*alpha1I*”, “*T-type calcium channel*”, “*CaVT*”).

(6)The effect of bicuculline (*12.5 microM*) on the spontaneous firing rate of *SCN neurons* during the night was heterogeneous due to the mixture of depolarizing and hyperpolarizing GABA(A)-mediated inputs during this period.
 (Experimental Unit: “*microM*”, Experimental Value “*12.5 microM*”, Neuron: “*SCN neurons*”, Brain Region “*SCN*”).

Named Entity Recognition

Once we had developed the corpus, we were able to use it to train and test tools for named entity recognition. We tested 3 methods as outlined earlier in this paper, representing a variety of techniques in the area of named entity recognition. In Table 4, we have highlighted the best performing system in terms of Precision, Recall and F1 score in bold font.

To produce the results in Table 4, we used the rules and dictionaries to generate named entities for the entire corpus, as these did not require any training data. We then split the full corpus into three partitions ‘train’, ‘test’ and ‘validate’ in the ratio 70%:15%:15%. We trained the CRF and Deep learning NER for each entity type using the training set, validated the hyper-parameters for the Deep Learning NER on the validation set and then tested both the CRF and Deep Learning NER on the test set. We performed no further tuning after we had generated the results on our test set. We used the same train and test set for both the CRF and Deep Learning NER, as this gives a fair comparison of their relative performance.

Table 4: The results of our methods to identify the entities in our corpus. We see that Deep Learning is the strongest approach for all entities except for Value.

Entity	Rules and Dictionaries			Conditional Random Field			Deep Learning NER		
	P	R	F1	P	R	F1	P	R	F1
Brain Region	0.324	0.304	0.314	0.880	0.772	0.822	0.856	0.833	0.844
Neuron	0.225	0.336	0.269	0.864	0.673	0.757	0.878	0.760	0.814
Model Organism	0.599	0.365	0.435	0.927	0.776	0.844	0.860	0.878	0.869
Ionic Channel	0.322	0.244	0.278	0.643	0.563	0.600	0.737	0.875	0.800
Ionic Current	0.128	0.109	0.118	0.853	0.580	0.690	0.872	0.680	0.764
Ionic Conductance	0.056	0.092	0.070	1.000	0.222	0.364	0.929	0.722	0.813
Value	0.264	0.320	0.289	0.897	0.839	0.867	0.895	0.828	0.860
Unit	0.256	0.544	0.348	0.915	0.942	0.929	0.904	0.957	0.930
Average	0.272	0.289	0.265	0.872	0.671	0.734	0.866	0.817	0.837

It is clear to see from Table 4 that the dictionary and rule based methods did not perform well, only capturing a fraction of cases. This implies that the dictionaries and rules we used were not able to capture the variety of named entities in the full corpus. The conditional random field performs much better than the rules and dictionaries, indicating that contextual information is important for the recognition of the entities that we are interested in. The deep learning NER performs better again than the CRF in most instances. The deep learning NER attains the highest F1 score for all entity classes, apart from the ‘Value’ class. The CRF approach often attains higher precision than the deep learning NER (Brain Region, Model Organism, Ionic conductance, Value, Unit). However this is outweighed by improved recall when using the deep learning NER to give higher F1 scores overall.

In the neuroinformatics literature, there are only two approaches that are directly comparable to ours. Firstly, French et al. (2009) developed a large corpus of brain region mentions and built a custom CRF to identify their named entities. This work was improved upon by Richardet et al. (2015), where new features were added to the CRF, leading to a slight increase in performance. To compare our best approach to this previous work, we trained the Deep Learning NER on the corpus provided by French et al. (2009). We show the results reported by the previous work, alongside our results in Table 5:

Table 5: Our results compared to previous state of the art for recognising Brain Regions.

Approach	Strict			Relaxed		
	P	R	F1	P	R	F1
French et al. (2009)	0.813	0.761	0.786	0.916	0.857	0.886
Richardet et al. (2015)	0.846	0.788	0.816	0.884	0.810	0.846

Deep Learning NER	0.821	0.815	0.818	0.934	0.927	0.931
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Discussion

Our corpus may seem small, containing annotated versions of 1000 sentences. Typically, tool performance is directly correlated to corpus size, and so the larger the corpus the better. However, we have taken the approach of using active learning in our work. Active learning allows us to extract only the most relevant parts of the documents that we are interested in. So, in our full corpus, we have 15 fully annotated abstracts (the seed set), the most relevant 500 sentences from 160 further abstracts and the most relevant 500 sentences from 15 full papers. The hypothesis of active learning is that by using selection criteria to extract the most useful sentences, we can gain a similar performance to annotating the full data set. The strong performance of our data-driven approaches implies that our active learning paid off, and that we were able to create a useful set of tools with a small corpus. If we were to perform further annotation to augment the corpus size (either using active learning or not), we would expect to see the performance of our tools increase. The limitation on performing further annotation is the time and cost associated with attaining high quality annotations from experts working in the field, as we have done in this work.

The agreement between the annotators is generally very high as shown in Table 3, attaining an aggregated accuracy of 0.837. This shows that the annotators agreed in most of the cases. It also indicates that the annotators broadly agreed about which entities should and should not be annotated (i.e., that true positives far outweighed false positives and false negatives). The agreement dips slightly for ionic channel, indicating that they found this class more difficult to agree upon than other classes. In the cases where disagreements arose between the annotators, we first attempted to resolve the dispute by discussing the discrepancies with the annotators. Where disagreements persisted, we deferred to the first, more senior, annotator's judgments.

The corpus we have created is principally useful for the training and testing of named entity recognition tools in the neuroscience domain. The corpus may be used by others to train their own tools, as well as to evaluate the performance of new tools with the same purpose. Other researchers may also wish to extend the corpus with new entity or relation types or indeed more documents to further improve the performance of the trained NER tools. To maximise reuse, the corpus will be made available via the OpenMinTeD platform⁴. Further to this, the partition we used for the train, test and validate sets will also be made available as part of the supplementary material to this work.

It is clear from our results in Table 4 that the approach we took using rules and dictionaries did not perform as well as could have been expected. There are two factors that may have influenced their performance. Firstly, the resource that we adopted to generate our dictionaries 'Neurolex' clearly did not contain sufficient cases to accurately capture the wide scope of named entities that were present in our corpus. This is unsurprising as the premise of our work is that manual curation of entities from the neuroscience literature is an arduous task, which requires many person hours and can be prone to mistakes. This shows the need for automation for the curation of entities in the neuroscience literature. The second factor that is likely to have influenced the results of the rules and dictionaries approach is the wide variation in the form of each term. Different authors use different ways of referring to the same entities and may use differing abbreviations for a term. These variational forms are difficult to capture with a dictionary, especially as they were not recorded and standardised in the resource that we used to get our lists of entities. The regular expressions also seemed to offer little in the way of performance. The expressions we used may have been overly simple and more complicated regular expressions could be used to capture other forms in which entities appeared.

We employed two data driven approaches for named entity recognition, namely NERSuite CRF and a deep learning system, which also used a CRF as its output layer. It is clear from our results in Table 4 that the two data driven approaches outperformed the resource driven approach based on dictionaries and regular expressions. The difference between these two approaches is that the NERSuite CRF and deep learning NER both are capable of learning features from the data that are useful for classifying the entities that we are interested in. For the NERSuite CRF, we start with a fixed set of features which are

⁴ <https://openminded.eu>

defined as part of the NERSuite system. The CRF is then capable of learning from the pre-labelled training data, which we provided to give the associations between the features and the labelled data. Typically, the CRF is very good at learning contextual features, which makes it very suitable for cases of named entity recognition where the terms typically occur with high variability of form, but low variability of context, as is the case for our entity types in neuroscience. For example, an author will typically mention the same types of words and word patterns in the context of neurons or brain regions and these act as clues that can be used to aid the CRF in classification. The NERSuite CRF performed well for all named entities apart from ionic conductance, where a high recall but low precision was observed. This is likely due to the low number of ionic conductances (n=76) in our data

The deep learning NER system again led to an increase in performance over the NERSuite CRF. This is in line with findings throughout the natural language processing literature, where deep learning methods have been shown to outperform traditional methods. The deep learning method takes the contextual associations that can be discovered by the learning algorithm a step further. Instead of relying on a set of pre-defined features (which may or may not be relevant to the specific NER case), the deep learning method instead uses word embeddings (which represent the context of a word as a dense information vector). These embeddings, along with character embeddings which encode orthographic relations are passed through a bi-directional LSTM, which extracts and combines the relevant parts of the information vector to create a new information vector that contains the most relevant parts of the information from the original embeddings. This process means that complex relations can be learnt between words in a sentence based not only on the words themselves, but also the words that may occur within the context of those words found in the sentence. The dense information vector is passed to a CRF layer as with the NERSuite CRF, which is capable of learning structured relations between the words. The increased performance of the Deep learning NER over the NERSuite CRF indicates that the Deep Learning NER was able to access more information about each named entity, and use this information to make better judgments on which words corresponded to named entities. This is expected as the Deep Learning NER uses word embeddings as its data source, which encode deep contextual information about each word and are richer than the features passed to the NERSuite CRF.

This work is undertaken as part of the EC funded H2020 project 654021: An Open Mining Infrastructure for Text and Data (OpenMinTeD). The OpenMinTeD project⁵ is developing a text mining framework which will integrate both a registry of corpora for text mining with a workflow service that allows text mining tools to be run on the corpora in question. To maximise the reusability of our work, the text mining components that we have developed for neuroscience will be made available via the OpenMinTeD platform. This will enable other researchers to directly use our tools in their own research.

Conclusion

We have developed a new corpus containing named entities for neuroscience. Our work represents the broadest attempt to perform named entity recognition for neuroscience to date (in terms of the total number of named entity types that we have explored). We used state of the art named entity recognition tools in the form of our Deep Learning NER system to develop text mining tools to detect the named entities that we have described in this paper. Further to this, we have compared our work with the existing state of the art, where we were able to show that our method outperformed previous techniques according to both a strict and a relaxed matching protocol. To extend this work, we will look to incorporate further entity types into our annotation scheme. We will also investigate techniques to identify mentions of synapses, as well as modelling parameters. Finally, we will look at identifying relations between the entities to further aid curation.

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⁵ <https://openminted.eu>

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